

Case No:

Tweet ID

Times retweeted

Date

Time

Suspended account?

01 Yes

02 No

Deleted/unavailable tweet?

01 Yes

02 No

Tweet type

01 Original tweet

02 Retweet

03 Quote tweet

04 Reply

[If Quote tweet] **Response to original tweet**

01 Agreement/endorsement

02 Disagreement

03 Mixed/qualification

04 Other

99 N/A

Gender

01 Male

02 Female

03 Other

04 Unidentified

Religion

01 Christian

02 Muslim

03 Hindu

04 Sikh

05 Buddhist

06 Jewish

07 Other

08 Atheist

99 Unidentified

Position on Muslims/Islam

01 Anti-Muslim

02 Supports Muslims

03 Mixed

04 Neutral/no view

Affiliation

- 01 Individual
- 02 State Institution/ Politician/Party
- 03 Leftist or Social justice advocacy groups
- 04 Alt/Far right group
- 05 Mainstream media organisation / journalist
- 06 Blogger/ alternative media organisation / journalist
- 07 Independent political analyst/commentator/author
- 08 NGO
- 09 Celebrity
- 10 Parody account
- 11 Academic
- 12 Mixed
- 13 Pressure group
- 14 Charity
- 15 Artist/Musician
- 16 Religious Representative
- 98 Other
- 99 Unidentified

Location

- 01 UK
- 02 US/ North America
- 03 Europe
- 04 South Asia (India, Pakistan, Bangladesh)
- 05 Other Asian countries
- 06 MENA region
- 07 Other African countries
- 08 Australasia/Oceania
- 09 South/Central America
- 10 Russia
- 11 Mixed (two or more locations are mentioned)
- 12 Other
- 99 None mentioned

Primary Topic**Secondary Topic**

01 Anti-Muslim, general ('Muslims are [negative trait]')

02 Anti-Muslim, specific (extremism, evil, radicalisation, anti-Quran, anti-Islamic scripture etc)

03 Islamist Terrorism

04 Islamification/ spread of Islam (Cultural clash, censorship, Islam taking over the world, conversion, attacks on 'our' culture, country, Shariah law, references to the movement of refugees, Muslim problem, cultural deviance)

05 Muslims provoked Christchurch attack

06 Islamophobia is denied/exaggerated

07 white victimhood

11 Pro-Muslim, general ('Muslims are [positive trait]')

12 Pro-Muslim, specific (contribution to society, acts of kindness, religion of peace, scientific endeavours etc)

13 Anti-Muslim discrimination/racism/ Islamophobia

14 survivor story/personal profile

15 Expressions of faith/prayers

16 Christchurch and British politics

17 Christchurch and US politics

18 Christchurch and Indian politics

19 Christchurch and NZ/Australia

20 Christchurch & global RW extremism

21 Politics, general

22 Pro conservative/right agendas

23 Anti conservative/right agendas

24 Pro Labour/ left agendas

25 Anti Labour/ left agendas / anti 'woke'

26 Pro-far right agenda

27 Anti far right agenda

28 Pro white supremacy

29 Anti white supremacy

30 Immigration/deportation

31 Community relations/cohesion

32 Condolences to victims

33 Political solidarity

34 Causes of terrorism

35 Process of radicalisation

36 Extremism online

37 Language & reporting terrorism

38 Gun crime/gun ownership

39 Protest

41 Left-wing criticism of mainstream media

42 Right-wing criticism of mainstream media

43 Tweet disseminates/premised on conspiracy theory

44 Tweet identifies/alleges conspiracy theory

45 accusation of antisemitism

46 antisemitism in content

99 Other

Hashtags – only coding content of tweet

Hashtag 1

Hashtag 2

Hashtag 3

1 7news

2 9news

3 alexandriaocasiocortez

4 asanother

5 auschwitz

6 auspol

7 awaninews

8 awanipagi

9 babystealers

10 banthewp

11 blexit

12 blog

13 breaking

14 brentontarrant

15 cdnpoli

16 christchruch

17 christchurch

18 christchurchattack

19 christchurchmassacre

20 christchurchmosque

21 christchurchmosqueattack

22 christchurchmosqueshooting

23 christchurchnz

24 christchurchshooting

25 christchurchshootings

26 christchurchterrorattack

27 christchurchterroristattack

28 christianterror

29 christianterrorism

30 copied

31 cristchurch

32 denial

33 eggboy

34 essay

35 fakenews

36 firstamendment

37 fixit

38 fraseranning

39 government

40 guncontrol

41 halifax

42 headscarfforharmony

43 heartbroken

44 hellobrother

45 hotelmumbai

46 imanibrahimabdelhalim

47 impeachtrump

48 insiders

49 islam

50 islamophobia

51 istandwithilhan

52 jacindaardern

53 jordanian

54 justice

55 justin

56 justsaying

57 khilafahprotectsmuslims

58 linwood

59 maga

60 medium

61 mfc

62 mosque

63 mosqueattack

64 muslim

65 muslimban

66 muslims

67 muslimsarenotterrorists

68 mynewneighbour

69 neuseeland

70 new_zealand

71 news

72 newzealand

73 newzealandmosque

74 newzealandmosqueattack

75 newzealandmosqueattacks

76 newzealandmosqueshooting

77 newzealandshooting

78 newzealandshootings

79	newzealandstrong	122	whitesupremacy
80	newzealandterrorattack	123	world
81	newzealandterroristattack	124	other
82	newzealandterroristattacks	125	none
83	newzeland		
84	nobelpeaceprize		
85	nstworld		URL? [in original content]
86	nz	01	Yes
87	nzmosqueshooting	02	No
88	nzpol		
89	onelove		Image(s)? [in original content]
90	opinion	01	Yes
91	pakistan	02	No
92	peace		
93	peacefulmosques		Icons/Emojis? [in original content]
94	phulwama	01	Yes
95	politics	02	No
96	prayforchristchurch		
97	prayfornewzealand		URL? [in Quoted content]
98	prayfornewzealandmoslem	01	Yes
99	proudtobemancunian	02	No
100	pslfinal	03	N/A
101	refugess	04	Unknown
102	respect		
103	secondamendment		Image(s)? [in Quoted content]
104	sikh	01	Yes
105	skylivenow	02	No
106	solidarity	03	N/A
107	stopviolenceagainstmuslims	04	Unknown
108	supportnzmuslims		
109	terror		
110	terrorism		Icons/Emojis? [in Quoted content]
111	terrorist	01	Yes
112	terroristattack	02	No
113	terroristattackinnewzealand	03	N/A
114	thevoiceau	04	Unknown
115	theyareus		
116	toronto		
117	toryislamophobia		
118	trump		
119	weareone		
120	westandtogether		
121	wherewasheradicalized		